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Endurance and Ecology: An Ecomasculine Reading of *The Old Man and the Sea*

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Abstract:

This paper explores Ernest Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea* from the perspective of eco-masculinity, an interdisciplinary approach that connects environmental ethics in relation to masculinity studies. The paper moves beyond the typical renditions of Hemingway's stoic and stern men, it argues that Santiago embodies a humiliated, empathetic, and spiritual man of the natural world, with help from R. W. Connell, Hultman and Pulé, as well as ecofeminist views, the paper analyses Santiago's relationship with the marlin, the sea and other creatures as a form of redefined, relational masculinity. By refusing traditional masculinity, this eco-masculine identity emphasises traits that include care and endurance in addition to a consciousness of the natural world. Using insights from eco-criticism, eco-feminism, and relational ethics, the paper provides a critique of the binary opposition between man and nature. The paper also contributes to the understanding of ecological masculinities and provides a careful analysis of *The Old Man and the Sea*, which relates literature to contemporary themes of the environment and gender.

Keywords: Eco-criticism, Eco-masculinity, Hemingway, Human-nature Relationship, Relational Masculinity.

Ernest Hemingway is a renowned American writer of short stories, who is also praised for his skills in journalism and sports. His works, often classified as classics of literature, are noted for abrupt prose style and journalistic quality, whereas his characters are known for a stoic, resilient attitude as they navigate through intense and psychologically affecting situations. “His writing is often referred to as tersely descriptive with staccato, clipped dialogue and characters affecting tough masculinity” (Jayakumar and Subramanian). The male characters in Hemingway’s works often exhibit emotional restraint, rarely expressing their emotions at any particular time. Jyoti Puri in *Critical Interpretation of Ernest Hemingway*, explains:

His sparse style conceals a complex subtext that ponders important issues like the state of humanity, masculinity, and the futility of war. He encourages readers to reflect on the underlying philosophical concerns that underlie his works through skeletal prose and subdued narrative (8).

The notion of the “code hero”, which explains a man thrust into an inevitability of suffering and death, who holds grace under pressure and exhibits stoicism with a touch of personal honour, is central to Hemingway’s literary ethos. Code Hero is “a recurrent archetype of a character in his writings, is a personification of stoicism and bravery in the face of difficulty” (Puri 9). This hero tends to ceaselessly occupy traditionally masculine domains: war, bullfights, big game hunting, or deep-sea fishing. However, the approach with which Hemingway has treated masculinity is more complicated than it seems. Though frequently vilified for his advocacy of machismo, his works have also been marked by the colours of weakness, breakdown and penetration of the natural world. “Hemingway's writing is characterised by an existentialist that arises from his characters' struggles with life's intrinsic meaninglessness” (Puri 9).

This engagement is even more profound in *The Old Man and the Sea* (1952), a novella that embodies Hemmingway's fascination with nature as opponent and friend. Santiago, the old fisherman at the centre of the story, represents many of Hemmingway's male ideals: tough-minded, lonely, sturdy-headed, but also contains a tender respect for the sea and its creatures. This intricate relationship of manhood with nature suggests a new interpretive angle based on eco-masculinity. Santiago does not aim to subdue the natural world ordinarily; rather, he enters the sea with respect and humility, knowing its force and grace. This respectful conversation he has with the marlin and his regret for its death indicates a masculinity of empathy, not of dominance. Even his interaction with other elements of the natural world, birds, stars currents speak out a spiritual intimacy. In this fashion, Hemmingway creates a model of manhood that is ecologically tuned and emotionally rich, providing informed soil for an Eco-masculinist reading. Zareen Usmani Farooq, in A BRIEF DISCUSSION ON HEMINGWAY'S RELATIONSHIP WITH NATURE, explains:

Hemmingway's relationship with nature was a deeply emotional and spiritual one, not just a literary theme. In times of emotional upheaval and bereavement, as well as a source of inspiration and renewal, nature provided him with solace. It offered him a blank canvas on which to investigate the intricacies of the human condition, the fragility of life, and the tenacity of the human spirit (39).

The novella, *The Old Man and the Sea* (1952) by Ernest Hemmingway narrates the story of Santiago, an old, poor Cuban fisherman who, "had gone eighty-four days now without taking a fish", goes out into the Gulf Stream for his last chance to get back his lost pride and demonstrate his strength. He lands a massive marlin, and after that, there are days and days of struggle between the man and the fish, one of physical strength, mental fortitude and quiet worth. The marlin is finally harpooned successfully by Santiago, but his triumph is brief as

sharks are attracted to the blood left while the fish is dragged home by the boy. He comes back home to his village, skinned bones of his catch, an exhausted man yet a spiritually strong man.

Although the novella is short, it is rich in symbolism and themes. It touches on timeless human concerns like isolation, resilience, ageing, and the sense of success or failure. Santiago is presented not as a victorious conqueror but as a still noble figure whose reason for living is in the struggle itself. His reverence for the marlin, his tender affections for the sea, and his keen appreciation of the cyclic patterns in nature defy old beliefs concerning masculine supremacy over nature (Hameed).

The natural world in the novella is not only a passive, minimalistic setting but a dynamic presence commanding personification and moral involvement. Santiago talks to birds, honours the fish he fights, and humbles himself to the power of the sea. These paradigms make *The Old Man and the Sea* the most amenable to Ecomasculinist reading, as it presents a picture of masculinity that values empathy, interdependency, and peace with nature. It offers a quiet but radical alternative to more forceful depictions of what it means to be a man in literature.

Masculinity studies are based on the idea that gender is a social construction and the theatrics of gender are fluid and unstable. Across various cultures, the norms of being masculine are different, which leaves us with no standard definition of masculinity but only with “the understanding that masculinities are structural, personal and unavoidably plural” (Hultman and Pule 18). R. W. Connell, in her book *Masculinities* challenges the monolithic concept of Masculinities, conceptualizing that there are various other types of Masculinities (Subordinate, Marginalised and Complicit) which do not fit the framework proposed by Hegemonic Masculinities, which Connell defines as “the formation of gender practices that establishes the dominance of man and subordination of woman” (Connell 77). Connell proposes that the privilege of hegemonic masculinity comes with power and access to

resources, but do all men have equal access to resources? Do all men have equal access to the environment to exploit it? And if they have access to natural resources, do all men want to exploit the natural environment? She says that the problem with normative masculinity is that “not many men actually meet the normative standards” (Connell 79).

Eco-Masculinity is therefore a considerate amalgamation of environmentalism and masculinity, rooted in and diverging from Eco-feminism. It maps out a possible link between masculinities and environmental action—one that is beneficial to the environment, nature and to mankind. Men end up being guardians and managers of the environment, thus reiterating a counterargument to eco-feminism. It also deconstructs the normative conceptions of Masculinities and “move towards reconfigurations of men and masculinities that stand shoulder to shoulder with the extensive and deeply considered works of gender and environments...” (18). It is considered to be a central feature of third-wave eco-criticism by Scott Slovic. Connell’s approach to Masculinities is realistic, empirical and expansive, because once the strict norms are rejected, men get “more space for broader, deeper and wider masculine care” (18). Paul also explains:

We do not question whether men care. We know they can and do. Like all human beings, men are caring, but are socialised to mete out their care within quite specific and tight parameters (9).

He also says,

On the contrary, we believe that all men (like all human beings the world over) can feel and express broader, deeper and wider care. However, we also recognise that, traditionally, the applications of men’s care are meted out unequally—advantaging a few, mostly Western white men—while causing harm to many (Western, non-Western and other-than-human) others (2).

Eco-masculinity is a novel reading of conventional masculine norms conceptualised through the lens of ecofeminist theory. Eco-feminism acknowledges the connection between depletion of natural resources and female exploitation in the context of patriarchy, and Eco-masculinity introduces a broader understanding by examining how various forms of male traits carry both environmental degradation and social injustice. It challenges the mainstream notions of masculinities through control, competition, and alienation from the natural world, and it advances those masculinities that emphasise caring, mutual support, and taking care of the earth. Eco-masculinity operates to (re)frame the idea of masculinity for ecology and social sustainability through working in tandem with ecofeminist perspectives. By redefining their masculinity thus, men are given an enabling mindset to help them contribute to deconstructing patriarchal systems and building better, more sustainable and equal partnerships with the environment and society. Victoria Addis sums up the same by saying, “Ecomasculinity, then, can be described as an expansion of the concept of masculinity within the framework of ecofeminism.”

There is a refusal of essentialist interpretations of eco-feminism, as discussed by Victoria Davion. It challenges the assumption that any experiential manifestations of masculinity are necessarily predicated upon patriarchal structures and helps to reveal the many and complex ways that masculinities relate to nature in particular real and literary environments. Hultman and Pulé in their works present what they call ecological masculinities by defining them as instances of masculine identity which emphasise care and stewardship for nearby ecologies as well as larger global environmental regimes, or what they refer to as the “glocal commons”. In this way, the importance of expanding the discourse on masculinities, to include those diverse and constantly changing characteristics, is emphasised, and so the need for a broader and inclusive vision of the way that masculinities relate to the natural environment is presented. As explained by Mark Allister:

There is no “nature” that is stable or foundational. And when we see that nature has numerous and shifting roles—sometimes existing as an idea, or as a commodity, or as the “pure” entity for those who want to attack what is more obviously human-made—then we are able to acknowledge how complex are the relations between this larger view of nature and masculinity (6).

There is a rich literary, cultural, and philosophical tradition that views nature in terms of a gendered scale. Nature is a feminine force, which is evidenced by fertility, emotion, nurturing, or chaos, while the male figure is described as rational, dominant, or orderly. This divide can be illustrated in pictures, such as “Mother Earth”, “virgin land”, or “wild woman”, each of which encapsulates a ruling idea that feminises, otherises and controls nature according to the same behaviours to women. Pederson explains, “the ‘Mother Earth’ metaphor was central to the organic theory of nature, an opposing image of nature as female was also prevalent; the wild and uncontrollable nature that could render violence, storms, and chaos”. This division has a rich literary tradition in which natural landscapes are perceived as symbols of how masculine identity is formed through forces and overcoming natural challenges. The relationship between men and their environment, as expressed in works of adventure fiction and poetic presentations of the countryside, also often signifies masculine persona in works of modernism. Such depictions strengthen the traditional gender roles, as well as the dominance over the environment is responsible for one’s strength and maturity (Kristi Pederson).

Eco-masculinity challenges established binaries and offers new versions of masculinity based on respect, compassion and connection with nature, rather than control or detachment. Dawning from eco-feminism, eco-masculinity questions the place that traditional masculine norms have had in the degradation of the environment and seeks to reshape ideas about manhood in ways conducive to ecological justice and ethical relations (Nightingale). Instead of starving man and nature apart, eco-masculinity emphasises the need to live together, be

vulnerable, and tend to mutual relationships. Here, nature is imagined as a resilient force with which men can interact empathetically and ethically, rather than as something to be controlled or conquered. Eco-masculinity as a literary analytical practice, particularly in such texts like *The Old Man and the Sea*, offers a deeper insight into the interpretation of male protagonists as friends, learners, and nurturers in relation to the environment. This view restages manhood from triumphant mastery to humility and involvement with the natural order.

Human-nonhuman relational ethics is emerging as a sub-discipline within environmental humanities addressing the political, moral, and emotional relations between people and the nonhuman environment—including animals, plants, ecosystems and natural forces. By decentring the human, this form of ethics encourages a system of existence that values the equality and deep interrelations that all beings have. It resists the conceptualisation of nature into mere objects and supports the claim that nonhuman objects have intrinsic value, autonomy, and the capacity to establish relationships with humans. (Chris Wilbert) Based on theories from eco-criticism to eco-feminism, animal studies and the cosmologies of indigenous communities, relational ethics promotes a shift from a relationship in nature rooted in control and exploitation to one grounded in reciprocity, compassion and responsibility. In literature, this framework has a special relevance because its representation of nature and living beings reflects underlying cultural perspectives on power, compassion, and cohabitation.

Human relations with nonhuman entities offer a pertinent tool for rethinking masculinity in the ecological context, according to the bias of the Eco-masculinity theory. Male identity has always been associated with alienation from nature, the subduing of wildness, the sharing in hunts, or ruling over land or sea. Through focusing on compassion, respect and the kinship bond, relational ethics is opposed to traditional masculine dealing with nonhuman others, advocating an approach free from control. It calls for a vision of masculinity based on sensibility, moral character, and awareness of ecological interconnectivity. The history of

Santiago in Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea* illustrates how this perspective encourages the characters to establish ethical and empathetic connections with nature, transforming old dogmas of power into sentiments and virtues. All these ethical relationships provide new perceptions on masculinity in literature, in terms of it not being an opponent to nature but a part of the whole (Madhumita Chatterjee).

Santiago's close relationship with nature is at the heart of *The Old Man and the Sea*, and it is a defining example of eco-masculine awareness. Although he is depicted in the traditional man as nature's conqueror image, Santiago interprets himself as part and parcel of nature. The narrator frequently compares him to nature when he says, "Everything about him was old except his eyes and they were the same color as the sea and were cheerful and undefeated" (1).

Santiago's affinity with nature, runs miles beyond merely supporting himself in terms of money. This relation is radically intimate, emotional, and existential. Fishing is not only his job but a kind of spiritual practice, a daily repetition that confirms his close relationship with the sea and its seasons. In choosing minimalism, isolation, and contemplative strength, Santiago makes a tangible commitment to nature, rather than profiting from material benefits. Santiago does not take advantage of nature. He is not apart from nature- he is a part of it. His life indeed forms a male profile of humble values, attached to a memory and a strong sense of belonging and thereby provides a meaningful picture of man's mastery and control over the natural world against the common backdrop. When the narrator says, "He was asleep in a short time and he dreamed of Africa when he was a boy and the long golden beaches and the white beaches, so white they hurt your eyes, and the high capes and the great brown mountains" (8), it showed his comfort in the fragrances of nature.

He is not an outside observer. Santiago is following his challenge with the marlin out of high respect. He says, "I wish I could feed the fish, he thought. He is my brother", freely admiring its fortitude and dignity, whereas he desires to haul it onto the shore. Such a partnership goes beyond the purposes of gain or control, transforming instead into a deep spirituality through experience of hardship to unite them. Similarly, Santiago understands the sea to be a woman, not only a handy thing, with which he could sustain, but an entity he treats with respect and speaks to, calling it "la mar", designating the loving relationship with the sea. How birds fly, how clouds float, how jellyfish and turtles swim, and he feels glad that the humanity's reach is limited when he says, "it is good that we do not have to try to kill the sun or the moon or the stars. It is enough to live on the sea and kill our true brothers"

Hemingway uses such gestures to create a character who identifies himself by his emotional honesty and mutual respect for all living beings, rather than dominating others. His reverential interaction with nature and his awareness of a common kinship with traditionally lower beings express Santiago's revision of masculinity focused on relational strength rather than on domination. Such a representation of Eco-masculinity is apt as it takes the male protagonist as an ethical participant and not as an exploitative force in the natural world. (Littlefield)

The wrestling between Santiago and the marlin is not one of asserting power, but it is a struggle that will bring out the sense of the spiritual connection on the part of the rivalling figures. The old man does not regard the fish as a prey to be conquered, but as an equal member of nature, worthy of respect, so to speak, using such phrases as "noble" and "brother". This prolonged engagement develops the form of a dialogue, based on mutual respect as well as resilience. Santiago says, "Fish," he said, "I love you and respect you very much. But I will kill you before this day ends" (19). Santiago neither seeks to dominate nature nor wants to develop a relationship that values and honours the marlin's power, beauty, and self. The confrontation

turns into an intense spiritual experience, where he can accept his definite strength and age, rather than a violent battle to be won, it becomes a challenge to his character. He says, “Now I will pay attention to my work and then I must eat the tuna so that I will not have a failure of strength”. In this narrative, Hemingway rejects the normative view of masculinities by depicting it as a practice of being in nature’s flow, hence taking an ecologically-based, ethical and eco-masculine way of thinking about relations of harmony and respect.

Santiago operates within a type of masculinity that transcends normal ideas of power and social status based on physical achievement and conventional ideas of manhood. Old, broken and isolated, his greatness is a capacity of perseverance, unpretentiousness and a quiet strength, all of which are often overlooked by current definitions of what a man should be. He is still modest because he never takes credit for previous achievements or seeks to be granted favour or insinuation of superiority. He appreciated fish’s power and called it more ‘masculine’. The narrator says, “It was considered a virtue not to talk unnecessarily at sea, and the old man had always considered it so and respected it”. He mingles with his troubles quietly, sustained by his inner principles and a great love for the environment. His quiet fortitude is opposed to the aggressive, youth-infused masculinity so many expect: power, conquest and assertion. Santiago represents a masculine identity through his rejection of conformity in the form of self-awareness, respect for nature and morality- all characteristic traits of eco-masculinity.

In the end, *The Old Man and the Sea* becomes an eco-tragedy and an incisive attack on the pride of humans, and the constraints that come with perceptions of what its manhood. The fight with the marlin, as all this majesty and persistence, by implication, medium, implies a feeble exaggeration of what human will can do. Although Santiago respects the fish greatly as well as the sea, he never does this with another person along with him, however he strives for his triumph, which is an old idea of conquering nature and being fulfilled through doing it. The

defeat of the marlin by the sharks represents the fragile nature of this worldview view, and as the natural force's strength cannot be conquered and conquered by man's desires. (Gurko)

By closing this, the novella converts Santiago's struggle from an exercise of strength to an opening for humility, articulating more compassionate, relational, and ecologically minded masculinities. Looking at Hemingway's novella from the perspective of eco-masculinity, we see condemnation of old-fashioned masculine ideals of dominance and conquest, and promotion of such values as stamina, empathy, and connection. Santiago's formally composed grace as the loser of the fish reveals the genuine source of strength: not ruling over nature, but realising our place in nature.

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